

**JOINT CONFERENCE
22 OCTOBER 2024**

INTEGRATING GENDER DIMENSION AND EQUALITY OBJECTIVES INTO ENERGY AND DEEP TECH FIELDS FOR INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

LESSONS FROM GENESYS AND NET4AIR ON INTEGRATING GENDER KNOWLEDGE INTO ENERGY TRANSITION AND DEEP TECH

POSITION PAPER

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<https://genesys-project.eu>

<https://net4air.eu/home/>

POLICY POSITION PAPER: ADVANCING GENDER EQUALITY IN ENERGY TRANSITION AND DEEP TECH RESEARCH & INNOVATION

Executive Summary

This policy position paper is based on the discussions held during the Joint Conference on 22 October 2024, organized by the Horizon Europe gEneSys and NET4Air projects ([the programme is available in Annex 1](#)). The conference highlighted the importance of integrating gender equality and the gender dimension in the research and innovation (R&I) processes related to energy transition and advanced technological innovations (deep tech). Despite the distinct focuses of the two projects—gEneSys on social and gender inequalities in energy transition and NET4Air on air pollution monitoring using deep tech—common ground was found in their shared commitment to ensuring that public investment in innovation contributes to both technological progress and social sustainability. This paper outlines key recommendations for policy actions to address these challenges, foster innovation, and meet the European Union’s gender equality and sustainability goals.

Background

The gEneSys project focuses on addressing gender and social inequalities in the energy transition, aiming to create fairer and more just outcomes. The NET4Air project, by contrast, works on advancing sensor technologies to measure air pollution, with an overarching awareness of environmental sustainability but without specific objectives related to gender dimension or equality. Both projects, however, align in the belief that technological innovation should not only advance technical applications but also contribute to social progress. This principle extends to the expectation that public investment in technology and research should reflect and promote social and gender equity.

Key Observations

1. Integrating Gender Dimensions in Research & Innovation

There is a critical need to integrate gender analysis in R&I processes. Without a clear focus on how gender influences or is influenced by R&I, there is the risk that technological advancements, especially in energy and deep tech sectors, could perpetuate or even exacerbate existing gender inequalities. For instance, technologies developed with assumptions of gender neutrality with respect to physiological or behavioural differences, e.g., user interfaces (wearable sensors, actionable devices), and AI applications, could have unintended negative impact on performance, affect acceptance or use, or risk safety. There is also a notable gender dependent bias in the perception of the benefits of new technologies and their services, possibly impacting the outcomes of tech-device evaluations by relying on the opinions of narrowly defined target groups (i.e., young white educated men).

2. Gender Knowledge in Higher Education and Training

To achieve the goals of the European Green Deal and the energy transition, there is a need to ensure that universities and research institutions produce the scientific and technological talent with the necessary social and gender knowledge. This knowledge is essential not only for sustainable technological development but also for creating tailored solutions that are inclusive and responsive to the needs of all social groups.

3. Policy Gaps and Opportunities for Gender Integration

While Horizon Europe has made strides in promoting gender equality in R&I participation and gender dimension in R&I content, there remains a significant gap in how researchers have responded to these goals, especially in the technology-focused fields, including deep tech. As innovation accelerates and opens-up opportunities for new markets for science knowledge, it is crucial to ensure that considerations of gender equality and gender dimension are systematically analysed from the earliest stages of research and development process, including in the conceptualization of project proposals.

4. Value of Interdisciplinary Collaboration to Advance Gender Knowledge in Research

The joint conference in Brussels highlighted the value of applying gender knowledge in research collaboration involving social sciences, humanities and STEM fields. Technology-oriented research, and the deep tech sectors in particular have been largely 'gender blind' and unfamiliar with gender analysis methods. But the gEneSys project has also revealed important gender gaps in the social science research on energy transition, which failed to explain the gender assumptions made when discussing socio-technical transformations.

Policy Recommendations

1. Enhancing Gender Knowledge in Horizon Europe

- **Action 1:** Encourage the European Commission (EC) to develop and implement well designed, rich in evidence, training materials for applicants, evaluators of proposals, and project monitors, with clear and systematic definitions of if and how the gender dimension should be analysed in the proposed research and its impact. Training should focus on questioning the assumption of gender neutrality and help reveal unconscious gender bias by showing scientific evidence that integrating gender analysis improves excellence and impact of research.
- **Action 2:** Strengthen the EU's commitment to advance gender equality and gender sensitive R&I by ensuring that all calls for proposals in the second stage of Horizon Europe and in FP10 include consideration of the gender dimension not just in the context of the proposed research or innovation but also in the anticipated impact of the project. It is possible that the research topic itself may be neutral with respect to the influence of sex/gender factors but when basic research or new technological innovations are motivated by applications in situations involving living things (health, environment) then it is necessary to consider if and how sex/gender may affect outcomes (e.g., acceptance, trust) or be affected in the impact (e.g., safety risk).

Action 3: Develop measures to ensure that universities and research institutions are training future researchers with the knowledge and tools to consider gender in all stages of energy transition and deep tech development. This includes integrating gender studies and social sciences in STEM curricula and fostering gender sensitive interdisciplinary approaches to research, including strategies for motivating and preparing young individuals to enter careers or research areas that are traditionally have been dominated by a single gender (e.g., women into engineering, men into nursing).

Action 4: Promote and support technology-focused programmes funded by the European Commission to actively consider and integrate gender equality benefits in all innovation projects motivated by social need, particularly those funded by Directorates-General (DGs) and agencies under the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) 2021–2027.

2. Policy Actions to Address Gender in Energy Transition

- Action 1: Engage R&I and policy advisors on energy transition, particularly within the European Green Deal framework, to promote gender knowledge in policy development. Encourage the integration of gender analysis in the design and implementation of energy transition programmes under Horizon Europe and FP10.
- Action 2: Challenge gender inequalities in energy-related decision-making, particularly where leadership and policy are predominantly male-dominated. Highlight the importance of considering diverse perspectives in policy and energy research to create equitable societal benefits. Introduce policies to encourage and foster gender balance in career choices.
- Action 3: Increase public education on energy as a techno-social system - not merely a technological issue - to recognise the importance of social acceptance of technological change, and promote the use social innovation to overcome male bias in energy research to ensure equitable outcomes for all groups in society.

3. Policy Actions to Address Gender in Deep Tech

- **Action 1:** Shift the narrative around deep tech, ensuring that it is not assumed to be gender neutral. Encourage a rigorous review of how advanced technologies like wearable diagnostic devices, and AI applications are developed, how they might be used and impact on their users, testing their effectiveness for diverse genders and ethnic groups, to avoid biased outcomes.
- **Action 2:** Promote the use of gender knowledge in the application of deep tech innovations, ensuring that early-stage technological research is not exempt from considering gender dimensions across the research and development process. Biased assumptions at early design stages will lead to suboptimal or inequitable solutions.
- **Action 3:** Facilitate the sharing of gender knowledge across different technological domains, particularly for strongly impacting fields like AI and machine learning, to ensure that gender dimensions are considered across the full spectrum of deep tech research.

Conclusion

The Joint Conference underscored the vital importance of advancing gender equality and integrating gender dimensions into all areas of research and innovation. It highlighted the need for more coordinated and systematic action from the European Commission, Higher Education sector, and research institutions to ensure that gender is not an afterthought but a key creativity-promoting and quality-ensuring criterion in R&I. This is not only essential for advancing gender equality but also for fostering innovation that contributes to more sustainable, equitable, and socially responsible technological advancements across all technology readiness levels. By embedding gender analysis in energy transition and deep tech R&I, the EU can ensure that its investments in innovation lead to inclusive progress that benefits all citizens.

Next Steps:

- Policy advocacy and engagement: Stakeholders from both the energy and deep tech sectors, as well as gender equality advocates, should collaborate to raise awareness and influence policymakers to adopt the recommendations outlined in this paper.
- R&I Actions: Encourage the organization of highly interdisciplinary conferences with dedicated discussions on gender, diversity, and inclusion issues, similar to the Brussels event, to facilitate the exchange of gender knowledge across intersectoral R&I projects.
- Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish robust mechanisms within the Framework Programmes to track the integration of gender dimensions in Horizon Europe projects, ensuring compliance with the proposed actions, the expected results, and assessing the impact of gender-sensitive R&I on societal and scientific progress.

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Brussels, 22 Oct 2024

AGENDA

9:30 - 10:00 ARRIVALS, NETWORKING, REFRESHMENTS

10:00 - 10:10 **WELCOMING** AND INFORMAL INTRODUCTIONS TO THE PROJECTS
gEneSys: *Lucio Pisacane*, CNR IRPPS (Italy), Coordinator
NET4Air: *Carmen Moldovan*, IMT (Romania), Coordinator

10:10 - 11:00 **POLICY ROUND TABLE: ADVANCING GENDER MAINSTREAMING AND RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION IN HORIZON EUROPE**

Luis Farina Busto, ERCEA. Working group Gender and Diversity
Marta Wysoczynska, Senior Policy Adviser in the Coordination and Analytics Team, EIC Department, EISMEA
Oriane Gilloz, Policy Officer in DG Research and Innovation - Gender Sector
Joana Simão Costa, Legal Officer DG Energy
Jeanne Lenders, Policy Officer DG Employment - Fair green digital transition

Moderator: *Martina Schraudner*, Fraunhofer, CERRI

11:00 - 11:20 COFFEE BREAK

11:30 - 13:00 **RESEARCH RESULTS AND LESSONS (SO FAR) FROM GENESYS**

Maria Camilla Fraudatario, CNR IRPPS. "What have we learned from literature about the nexus between gender and energy"
Antonio De Nicola, ENEA. "Gender gaps in knowledge communities"
Yara Evans, Imperial College. "Gender gaps in SSH recommendations"
Tadeusz Rudek, Jagiellonian University. "Gender gaps in textbooks and curricula"
Cloe Mirenda, CNR IRPPS. "NRRPs gaps in promoting a just and gender-sensitive energy transition"
Nana Klutse, AIMS. "Gaps and omissions in EU-AI cooperation on R&I" (recorded speech)

Moderator: *Clemens Striebing*, Fraunhofer, CERRI

13:00 - 14:00 LUNCH, NETWORKING, PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITIES

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14:00 - 15:45

GENDER DIMENSION CHALLENGES AND POLICIES IN DEEP TECH IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

Toshiyasu Ichioka, Director, RIKEN Europe Office. "Case studies for Europe and beyond"

Eefje Vandamme, Intellectual Matters BV. "Gender dimension in tech Innovation"

Simona Aracri, CNR INM. "A Route to Equality, Diversity, and Inclusivity in Soft Robotics"

Mircea Modreanu, Tyndall National Institute-University College Cork. "Addressing gender dimension in a deep tech Institution"

Clara-Mihaela Ionescu, Ghent University, ERC Grantee. "Sustainability of Gender dimension"

Moderator: *Melanie Timpel*, CNR IMEM

15:45 - 16:15

COFFEE BREAK, PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITIES

16:15 - 16:45

CONSOLIDATING KNOWLEDGE ON THE INTERACTIONS BETWEEN TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIETY. WHAT'S NEXT?

Clemens Striebing, Fraunhofer, CERRI

Monica Favaro, CNR ICMATE

16:45 - 17:30

Q&A, OPEN DISCUSSION, AND IDEAS FOR THE POSITION PAPER

Panellists: EC, gEneSys, NET4Air

Moderators: *Sabrina Presto*, CNR ICMATE and *Elizabeth Pollitzer*, PORTIA

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Deep tech and sustainable energy are crucial for the future as they drive innovations that address global challenges such as climate change, resource scarcity, and societal wellbeing. Deep tech, with its focus on advanced technologies like AI, communication technologies, photonics and optoelectronics, quantum computing and biotechnology, has the potential to revolutionize industries, enhance efficiency, and create new economic opportunities. Tackling the energy crisis and making effective transition to low-carbon economies are among the most essential challenges societies face today. The aim of this conference is to show how gender equality objectives can be integrated into the socio-technical pathways to inclusive and sustainable future.

Women are significantly underrepresented in both the deep tech and energy transition fields as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, decision makers, and leaders. The average share of women in the R&I workforce in energy sector companies in the EU27 is 22% (CINEA 2024). Only 14% of founders in deep tech startups are women. An important current policy driver for gender equality in the EU is the commitment in the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027 for mainstreaming gender into the budgets of all funded programmes.

The conference aims to examine gender dimension in both green and digital transitions, to shape interactions between technology and society, and new understanding how to integrate gender equality as a significant objective of technologically focused interventions. The event targets science policy and decision makers and advisers, domain experts, researchers and innovators, promoting knowledge for social progress.

The conference is jointly organized by the two EU funded HorizonEurope projects gEneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) and NET4Air (Advanced nanotechnology-based devices and smart systems integration in environmental monitoring)

The meeting is intended to be interactive, participatory activities are encouraged to coproduce a position paper to be published.

[REGISTRATION HERE](#)

Joint Conference
22 October 2024

Scotland House Round Point Robert Schuman 6
1040 Brussels